

Science
Conference
2026

13–14 Feb 2026

International **scientific and practical conference**

- 1. Scientific technologies**
- 2. Economy**
- 3. Finance**
- 4. Mathematical analysis**
- 5. Technical sciences**
- 6. Pedagogy**
- 7. Psychology**
- 8. Philosophy**
- 9. Natural Sciences**

zenodo

OpenAIRE | EXPLORE

www.d-prensa.com

International scientific and practical conference

Part 1
February 2026

Collection of Scientific Works

© International scientific and practical conference. 2026.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of rapid globalization and technological transformation, the development of science and practical knowledge has become one of the most decisive factors in ensuring sustainable progress. The International Scientific and Practical Conference provides a global platform for scholars, researchers, and practitioners to share their innovative ideas, theoretical insights, and applied research outcomes in a multidisciplinary environment.

The conference covers a wide range of research fields, including scientific technologies, economics, finance, mathematical and technical sciences, pedagogy, psychology, philosophy, and natural sciences. Such an interdisciplinary approach fosters collaboration between representatives of different scientific schools and contributes to the integration of academic research into real-world practice.

The main objective of this conference is to stimulate scientific dialogue, enhance international cooperation, and encourage the dissemination of cutting-edge research results. Each presented study is expected to address current global challenges, propose practical recommendations, and open new perspectives for the advancement of science and education.

By bringing together diverse academic and professional communities, this conference aims to strengthen the link between theory and practice, promote innovation, and support the formation of a modern scientific culture based on openness, critical thinking, and cross-border collaboration.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

International scientific and practical conference. International scientific and Applied Research. 13.02.2026.

© International scientific and practical conference. 2026.

UDC: 001.891

TURIZMDA XORIJIY TILLARNING O‘RNI VA AHAMIYATI

G‘aybulloyev SH.T. – O‘zMU Jizzax filiali “Filologiya va tillarni o‘qitish: ingliz tili”
yo‘nalishi talabasi

Ilmiy rahbar: Saitov S.A – O‘zMU Jizzax filiali dotsent v.b.
shakhriyor16me@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: Hozirgi globallashtirish davrida tilshunoslik bilimlari nafaqat ijtimoiy, balki iqtisodiy sohalarining ham ajralmas qismiga aylanib bormoqda, ayniqsa dinamik rivojlanayotgan turizm sektorida. Ushbu tadqiqot tilshunoslikning turizm sanoatidagi fundamental o‘rni va ahamiyatini chuqur tahlil qilishga qaratilgan. Unda turli madaniyatlarni bog‘lovchi ko‘priklar sifatida tilning vazifasi o‘rganiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Termin, Turizm, Iboralar, Tilshunoslik, Mintalitet, Tarjima, Lingua madaniyat, Tarjimon, Gid hamrohligi.

Annotation: In the current era of globalization, linguistic knowledge is becoming an integral part of not only social but also economic spheres, especially in the dynamically developing tourism sector. This research is aimed at a deep analysis of the fundamental role and significance of linguistics in the tourism industry. It examines the function of language as a bridge connecting different cultures. The primary focus is on enhancing the quality of tourism services, terminological accuracy, and communicative efficiency through the principles of linguistics.

Key words: Linguistics, Tourism, Terminology, Translation, Guide Assistance, Linguaculture, Interpreter.

Bugungi globallashtirish sharoitida turizm sohasi boshqa ko‘plab sohalar qatori o‘ziga xos tilshunoslik terminlari va atamalar tizimiga ehtiyoj sezadigan muhim yo‘nalishlardan biri hisoblanadi. Chunki turizm turli millat, elat va madaniyat vakillari o‘rtasidagi bevosita muloqotga asoslanadi. Bunday muloqot esa har bir xalqning diniy e‘tiqodi, dunyoqarashi, urf-odatlar va ijtimoiy hayot tarzi bilan chambarchas bog‘liq holda amalga oshiriladi. Shu bois sayyohlar bilan ishlovchi gidlar va tarjimonlarning til bilimi, madaniy saviyasi hamda kasbiy mahorati alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Hozirgi davrda tarjima faoliyati tilshunoslik fanining ajralmas tarkibiy qismiga aylangan. Tarjima tillar o‘rtasidagi o‘zaro munosabatlarni tartibga soluvchi muhim vosita bo‘lib, u turli tillarning o‘xshash va farqli jihatlarni aniqlashga, ularning grammatik, leksik va uslubiy xususiyatlarini chuqurroq anglashga yordam beradi. Ayniqsa, turizm sohasida tilshunoslikning ta‘siri tarjima jarayonida, madaniyatlararo muloqotda yuzaga keladigan farqlarni tushuntirishda hamda tillarning funksional imkoniyatlaridan to‘g‘ri foydalanishda yaqqol namoyon bo‘ladi. Shundan kelib chiqib aytish mumkinki, tarjima va tilshunoslik bir-biri bilan uzviy bog‘langan, o‘zaro bir-birini to‘ldiruvchi sohalaridir. Bejizga turizm yo‘nalishida faoliyat yuritayotgan mutaxassislariga tilshunoslikning fonetika, leksikologiya, stilistika, pragmatika va lingvokulturologiya kabi bo‘limlari bo‘yicha bilim va ko‘nikmalar berilmaydi. Chunki tarjima jarayonini samarali amalga oshirish yoki ekskursiya davomida xorijiy sayyohlar bilan to‘g‘ri muloqot o‘rnatish uchun tanlangan xorijiy til birliklarini puxta o‘rganish va ularni lingvomadaniy tahlil asosida talqin qilish muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bundan tashqari, madaniyatlararo farqlarni to‘liq anglash uchun matn yoki

nutqning asl mazmunini, ya'ni xalq mentalitetini buzmaganda tushuntirish va yetkazish talab etiladi. Turizm sohasida lingvomadaniyat alohida o'rin tutadi, chunki u xalqning nafaqat bugungi kundagi turmush tarzini, balki asrlar davomida shakllanib kelgan milliy, tarixiy va diniy qadriyatlarini ham o'zida aks ettiradi. Ma'lumki, har bir til o'z madaniyatiga xos bo'lgan folklor namunalari, janrlar, maqollar, iboralar va xalq og'zaki ijodi bilan boydir. Ushbu bo'liklar o'sha tilda so'zlashuvchi millatning eng qimmatli va avloddan-avlodga asrab-avaylab kelinadigan ma'naviy merosi hisoblanadi. Ana shunday madaniy merosni sayyohlarga to'g'ri, aniq va asl mohiyatini saqlagan holda yetkazish katta mas'uliyatni, shuningdek, uzoq yillik tajriba, chuqur bilim va amaliy ko'nikmalarni talab etadi.

Bugungi kunda turizm oddiy sayohat bilan cheklanib qolmay, turli xalqlar o'rtasida madaniy ko'prik vazifasini bajarayotgan muhim sohalaridan biriga aylandi. Har bir sayyoh yangi mamlakatga kelar ekan, u nafaqat tarixiy obidalarini ko'rishni, balki o'sha xalqning hayot tarzi, qadriyatlari va dunyoqarashi bilan yaqindan tanishishni istaydi. Ana shu jarayonda til va muloqot muhim rol o'ynaydi. Aynan gid va tarjimonlar sayyohlar uchun mamlakatning "ovoziga" aylanadi. Shu sababli turizm sohasida ishlayotgan mutaxassislar uchun xorijiy tilni bilish juda muhim, ammo bu yetarli emas. Tilni bilish bilan birga, uning ortida turgan madaniyatni tushunish ham zarur. Chunki bir til orqali ifodalangan so'z yoki ibora boshqa madaniyatda butunlay boshqa ma'noni anglatishi mumkin. Agar gid yoki tarjimon buni inobatga olmasa, sayyoh noto'g'ri tushuncha hosil qilishi yoki o'zini noqulay his qilishi mumkin. Tarjima jarayonida bunday holatlar tez-tez uchraydi. Masalan, milliy taomlar nomi, urf-odatlar, marosimlar yoki diniy tushunchalarni so'zma-so'z tarjima qilish ko'pincha maqsadga muvofiq bo'lmaydi. Bunday vaziyatlarda tarjimon tushuntirish yo'lini tanlaydi, ya'ni so'zning ma'nosini emas, balki mazmunini yetkazishga harakat qiladi. Bu esa tarjimondan keng dunyoqarash, sabr va muloqot qobiliyatini talab etadi. Gidning nutqi va o'zini tutishi ham sayyohlar taassurotida katta o'rin tutadi. U faqat ma'lumot beruvchi shaxs emas, balki mehmonlar bilan do'stona aloqa o'rnatuvchi insondir. Gidning ohangi, yuz ifodasi, tanlagan so'zlari va hatto hazil-mutoyibasi ham muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ayrim madaniyatlarda ochiq hazil yaxshi qabul qilinsa, boshqalarida bu noo'rin bo'lishi mumkin. Shu bois har bir vaziyatda ehtiyotkorlik va hurmat muhimdir. Zamonaviy turizm yozma tarjima ham katta rol o'ynaydi. Mehmonxona ma'lumotlari, reklama bukletlari, sayohat dasturlari va internet saytlardagi matnlar sayyohda mamlakat haqidagi dastlabki tasavvurni shakllantiradi. Agar bu matnlar murakkab, sovuq yoki xatolar bilan to'la bo'lsa, mehmonning qiziqishi pasayadi. Aksincha, sodda, samimiy va tushunarli tilda yozilgan matnlar sayyohni o'ziga tortadi va ishonch uyg'otadi. Bundan tashqari, turizm sohasida madaniyatlararo hurmat masalasi juda muhim. Har bir xalqning o'z qadriyatlari, muqaddas tushunchalari va e'tiqodlari bor. Gid va tarjimonlar bu jihatlarni hisobga olib, sayyohlarga to'g'ri yo'l-yo'riq ko'rsatishi kerak. Masalan, kiyinish madaniyati, ibodat joylarida o'zini tutish qoidalarini yoki mahalliy urf-odatlar haqida oldindan tushuntirish berish ko'plab tushunmovchiliklarning oldini oladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, turizm sohasida til, tarjima va madaniyat bir-biridan ajralmas tushunchalardir. Tarjima xalqlar o'rtasidagi masofani qisqartiradi, madaniyat esa bu muloqotni mazmunli qiladi. Tilni biladigan, madaniyatni his qiladigan va odamlar bilan samimiy muomala qila oladigan mutaxassislar turizm rivojining asosiy tayanchidir. Shu bois kelajakda turizm kadrlarini tayyorlash jarayonida faqat bilimga emas, balki insoniylikka, madaniy sezgirlikka va muloqot madaniyatiga ham katta e'tibor qaratish lozim.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

1. G'ofurov I. Tarjimonlik mutaxassisligiga kirish-T. Mehridaryo, 2008. Jo'rayev K.

2. Yo'ldoshev, M. Turizm sohasida muloqot va nutq madaniyati. Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 2019.
3. Islomov, Z. Turizm terminologiyasi va tarjima masalalari. Toshkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2021.
4. Snell-Hornby, M. Translation Studies: An Integrated Approach. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 2006.
5. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Turizm va madaniy meros vazirligi. Turizm xizmatlarida gid va tarjimonlar faoliyatiga qo'yiladigan talablar. Toshkent, 2022.
6. Newmark, P. A Textbook of Translation. New York: Prentice Hall, 1988.
7. Cohen, E. Tourism and Cultural Change. Clevedon: Channel View Publications, 2004.
8. Eshboyeva M., Eshboyev T., Saitov S. GREEN ACCOUNTING IN UZBEKISTAN: SUSTAINABILITY AND INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL REPORTING STANDARDS //Scientific journals" D-PRESS SERVICES". – 2025. – T. 1. – №. 7. – C. 88-91.
9. Saitov S., Nuraliyeva S. BOZOR IQTISODIYOTIDA PSIXOLOGIK BOSHQARUV SHAKLLARI //Scientific practical conference. – 2025. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 447-452.
10. Saitov S., Asrayev S. MECHANISMS FOR INCREASING EMPLOYMENT THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP //Scientific practical conference. – 2025. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 335-339.
11. Saitov S. et al. ZAMONAVIY FILOLOGIYA FANLARIDAGI DOLZARB MASALALAR //Scientific practical conference. – 2025. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 419-422.
12. Nasrullayeva S., Saitov S. RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASRIDA SUN'IY INTELLEKTNING JAMIYAT RIVOJI, INSON FAOLIYATI VA IJTIMOY-IQTISODIY JARAYONLARDAGI O 'RNI //Scientific practical conference. – 2025. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 105-108.